

IDENTIFICATION OF BRAIN TUMOR USING NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT: Brain tumor classification is a crucial task to evaluate the tumors and make a treatment decision according to their classes. There are many imaging techniques used to detect brain tumors. However, MRI is commonly used due to its superior image quality and the fact of relying on no ionizing radiation. Deep learning (DL) is a subfield of machine learning and recently showed a remarkable performance, especially in classification and segmentation problems. In this paper, a DL model based on a convolutional neural network is proposed to classify different brain tumor types using two publicly available datasets. The former one classifies tumors into (meningioma, glioma, and pituitary tumor). The other one differentiates between the three glioma grades (Grade II, Grade III, and Grade IV). The datasets include 233 and 73 patients with a total of 3064 and 516 images on T1-weighted contrast-enhanced images for the first and second datasets, respectively. The proposed network structure achieves a significant performance with the best overall accuracy of 96.13% and 98.7%, respectively, for the two studies. The results indicate the ability of the model for brain tumor.

KEYWORDS: Brain tumor, Convolution neural network, data augmentation, deep learning, MRI.

I.INTRODUCTION

Brain tumor can be defined as unnatural and uncontrolled growth in brain cells. Since the human skull is a rigid and volume limited body, consequently, any unexpected growth may affect a human function according to the involved part of the brain; moreover, it may spread into other body organs and affect human functions [1]. According to the world cancer report published by the World Health Organization (WHO), brain cancer accounts for less than 2% of human cancer;

however, severe morbidity and Complications are produced. Cancer research corporation in the United Kingdom mentioned that there are about 5,250 deaths annually by the act of brain, other Central Nervous System (CNS) and intracranial tumors in the UK. Brain tumors can be classified in many ways, for instance, primary and secondary tumors. The former represents about 70% of all brain tumors, while secondary tumors are the residuals 30% [2].

This classification is determined according to tumors origin just as tumors first originate in the brain are called primary tumors. On the other side, tumors first arise in any other part of the body and then transferred to the brain are called secondary tumors, and most of them are malignant. Numerous imaging techniques can be used to detect and classify brain tumors. However, MRI is one of the most common non-invasive techniques. MRI popularity comes from the fact of using no ionizing radiation during the scan as well as its superior soft-tissue resolution plus the ability to acquire different images using various imaging parameters or by employing contrast-enhanced agents [3].

Gliomas are the most prevalent type of brain tumors that originate in the glial cells of the brain . Gliomas include 30% of all brain tumors and CNS, and 80% of all malignant brain tumors. Gliomas classified into four grades according to the WHO starting from type I to IV. Grade I tumors are benign and have a much similar texture of the normal

glial cells, Grade II is a slightly different in texture, Grade III tumors are malignant with abnormal tissue appearance while grade IV is the most severe stage of gliomas and tissue abnormalities that can be visualized by naked eye [4-5].

Meningioma is a tumor that forms on the membrane that covers the brain and spinal cord inside the human skull and grows placidly. Most of meningioma tumors are benign. However, pituitary tumor starts from the pituitary glands that control hormones and regulate functions in the body. It can be benign, benign that expands to bones, and malignant. Complications of pituitary tumors may cause permanent hormone deficiency and vision loss.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In recent years a great effort of the research in field of medical imaging was focused on brain tumors segmentation. The automatic segmentation has great potential in clinical medicine by freeing physicians from the burden of manual labelling; whereas only a quantitative measurement allows to track and modelling precisely the disease. Despite the undisputed usefulness of automatic tumor segmentation, this is not yet a widespread clinical practice, therefore the automatic brain tumor segmentation is still a widely studied research topic.

The main difficulties in field of automatic tumor segmentation are related to the fact that the brain tumors are very heterogeneous in terms of shape, color, texture and position and they often deform other nearby anatomical structures. An healthy brain has a strong sagittal symmetry, that is weakened by the presence of tumor. The comparison between the healthy and ill hemisphere, considering that tumors are generally not symmetrically placed in both hemispheres, was used to detect the anomaly.

One of the motivations to make the substandard segmentation of good organization is the occurrence of artefact in the MR images. One such artefact is the additional cranial tissues(skull). These additional cranial tissues repeatedly hamper with the ordinary tissues throughout segmentation that accounts for the substandard segmentation efficiency. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is an advanced medical imaging technique used to produce high resolution images of the parts contained in the human body.

MRI imaging is often used when treating brain tumors. These high resolution images are used to examine human brain development and discover abnormalities. Nowadays there are several methodologies for classifying MR images. Among all medical image processing, image segmentation is initial and important work, for example, quantification of specified area must based on accurate segmentation. A tumor is a mass of tissue that grows out of control of the normal forces that regulates growth. The multifaceted brain tumors can be split into two common categories depending on the tumors beginning, their enlargement prototype and malignancy.

Primary brain tumors are tumors that take place commencing cells in the brain or commencing the wrapper of the brain. An inferior or metastatic brain tumor takes place when cancer cells extend to the brain from a primary cancer in a different component of the body. The majority of investigations in developed countries demonstrate that the amount of people who develop brain tumors and depart this life from them has greater than before maybe as much as 300 over past three decades.

The computationally efficient method runs orders of magnitude faster than current state

of the art techniques giving comparable or improved results. Our quantitative results indicate the benefit of incorporating model aware affinities into the segmentation process for the difficult case of brain tumor. This paper expresses a well-organized technique for automatic brain tumor segmentation for the removal of tumor tissues from MR images. A well acknowledged segmentation trouble within MRI is the task of category voxels according to their tissue type which take account of White Matter (WM), Grey Matter (GM), Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) and occasionally pathological tissues like tumor etc.

Removing the tumor from brain images is a challenging task and it has a wide variety of applications in real time. Some of the methods for removing from images are by using preprocessing, convolution operation, max pooling layer and fully connected network. Low rank appearance model, image super-resolution, restoring the image with convolutional neural networks, deep residual learning and these methods are described below.

Preprocessing operation:

Before feeding the images into the proposed structure, a preprocessing step is performed. The first process is to downsize the original image from $512 \times 512 \times 1$ pixels into $128 \times 128 \times 1$ pixels in order to decrease dimensionality, computations and help the network to show a better performance in lower time and more straightforward calculations. Then, data is shuffled before splitting them to maintain the system to train on unsorted data and prevent focusing on a narrow band of the entire dataset. Data is divided into three sections; training, validation, and test sets all with their individual target labels (68% for training and 32% for system test and validation).

Finally, we augment the images of study I so that the system can identify them as new ones, and that is usually used to avoid over fitting and increase model robustness. original one; changes include flipping around the x-axis, right/left mirroring, adding salt noise and image rotation by 45 degrees for study I. By doing this augmentation process, we have increased the original 3064 images by a factor of 5, so the final dataset became 15,320 images for study I and 516 images for study II.

Convolution operation extract the features from the input image:

The filters slide over the image with vertical and horizontal steps called stride (S). Padding (P) of the original images may happen before sliding the filters in order to maintain information at the edges. These kernels are used as features identifiers; such that kernels in the early layers detect only low-level features like (edges, lines and blobs), while advanced ones are used to detect more and more complex features

Image Super-Resolution Using Deep Convolution Networks:

A deep learning method was proposed for single image super-resolution (SR). This method directly learns an end-to-end mapping between the low/high-resolution images. The mapping is represented as a deep convolutional neural network (CNN) that takes the low-resolution image as the input and outputs the high-resolution one. This method further shows that traditional sparse-coding-based SR methods can also be viewed as a deep convolutional network. But unlike traditional methods that handle each component separately, this method jointly optimizes all layers.

The deep CNN has a lightweight structure, yet demonstrates state-of-the-art restoration quality, and achieves fast speed for practical

on-line usage. The different network structures were explored and parameter settings to achieve trade-offs between performance and speed. Moreover, our network was extended to cope with three color channels simultaneously, and show better overall reconstruction quality

III. PROPOSED METHOD

Figure (1) shows the block diagram of the proposed method, in which the system starts to load and extract images and labels from datasets raw files and then make a preprocessing and augmentation techniques just after splitting the dataset into training, validation and test sets

Fig. 1: Block diagram of the proposed method.

Then, the structure of the proposed method is introduced, followed by setting the hyper-parameters, regularization techniques, and optimization algorithm. Finally, network training and performance computations are presented.

A dataset used in this work has two different datasets. The first one is acquired from Nanfang Hospital and General Hospital, Tianjing Medical University, China from 2005 to 2010, and then published online with various versions since 2015 reaching to its last release in 2017. The database

includes T1-weighted contrast-enhanced images acquired from 233 patients with three types of brain tumors that are meningioma, glioma, and pituitary tumor. Brain tumors can be different in shape, location, and size according to their types and grades. The dataset includes three different views: axial, coronal and sagittal view.

The second dataset is obtained from The Cancer Imaging Archive (TCIA) public access repository. The Repository of Molecular Brain Neoplasia Data (REMBRANDT) contains MRI multi-sequence images from 130 patients with different diseases, grades, races, and ages. Before feeding the images into the proposed structure, a preprocessing step is performed. The first process is to downsize the original image from $512 \times 512 \times 1$ pixels into $128 \times 128 \times 1$ pixels in order to decrease dimensionality, computations and help the network to show a better performance in lower time and more straightforward calculations.

Then, data is shuffled before splitting them to maintain the system to train on unsorted data and prevent focusing on a narrow band of the entire dataset. Data is divided into three sections; training, validation, and test sets all with their individual target labels (68% for training and 32% for system test and validation). Finally, we augment the images of study I so that the system can identify them as new ones, and that is usually used to avoid overfitting and increase model robustness.

CNN architecture is proposed to classify different types and grades of brain tumors. The architecture of the network is evolved using different configuration to acquire the most appropriate structure.

IV. RESULTS

Fig.2: input image

Fig.3: conv.image1

Fig.4: conv.image2

Fig.5: Max pooling 1

Fig.6: Max pooling 2

Fig.7: Tumor outline

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a CAD system for the classification of brain tumor MR images into three types (meningioma, glioma, and pituitary) in one study, and further classifying of gliomas into different grades using a custom deep neural network structure. The proposed network is constructed from 16 layers starting from the input layer which holds the preprocessed images passing through the convolution layers and their activation functions (3 convolution, 3 Re LU, normalization and 3 Max pooling layers). Additionally, two dropout layers are used to prevent over fitting followed by a fully connected layer and a soft max layer to predict the output and finally a classification layer that produces the predicted class. Although the dataset is relatively not big (due to the variety of imaging views), data augmentation helped well to show better results and hence overcome this problem. Our proposed architecture has achieved the highest accuracy of 96.13% and 98.7% concerning the two datasets used in this paper.

VI. REFERNCES

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